

AmI HMAS: goal-driven interaction support in Smart Environments

Alexandru Sorici¹, Victor-Vasile Udristioiu¹, and Adina Magda Florea¹

National University of Science and Technology POLITEHNICA Bucharest, Splaiul
Independentei 313, Bucharest, Romania
{alexandru.sorici, adina.florea}@upb.ro,
victor.udristioiu@stud.acs.upb.ro

Abstract. Goal-driven interaction in Smart Environments has been a long standing desire in Ambient Intelligence (AmI) use cases. Recent advances in web-based MAS and foundational machine learning models that can power agent planning and reasoning are making goal-driven interaction frameworks realistically plausible. We demonstrate a prototype framework for management of goal-driven AmI interactions that builds upon: (i) Hypermedia MAS environment modeling, (ii) resource signification to capture experience of use and (iii) LLM support for agent reasoning. We showcase framework functionality on hand of a smart office simulated scenario.

Keywords: Ambient Intelligence · Hypermedia MAS · Web-of-Things · AI Agents · Context and Signification

1 Introduction

Goal-driven interactions have been an early vision in the Ambient Intelligence (AmI) domain [11]. The topic remained largely out of practical reach, due largely to challenges such as a large diversity of device and service capabilities, as well as the insufficient reasoning capabilities of systems intended to bridge these capabilities together towards a user goal.

However, the topic is receiving renewed interest from both academia and industry, thanks to recent developments in AI foundational models (notably Large Language Models - LLMs). LLMs have demonstrated emergent capabilities for intent understanding, planning (in complex domains requiring neuro-symbolic approaches [13], as well as simpler ones related to activities of daily living [15]) and matching of natural language actions to APIs [16, 12]. Furthermore, efforts within the W3C Web Agents Community Group [8] have surfaced Hypermedia MAS as a design paradigm in which the agent environment and agent capabilities obtain a *representation* over the web. This view allows new agents and existing web services and devices to interact more uniformly within an application.

In this context, systems that leverage LLM reasoning capabilities are starting to be explored. Sasha [14] looks at using LLMs to control smart home devices

handling common automation routines (e.g. as found in typical If-This-Than-That recipes [5]). The work finds that LLM generated plans can fail when the user request is poorly- or under specified (e.g. "make it cozy in here"), leading to the need of an iterative reasoning process that encompasses clarifying, filtering, planning, and feedback steps. While Sasha is an analytic study, LLMind [10] goes a step further, presenting an LLM-based task-oriented AI agent framework, enabling collaboration between IoT devices, based on human high-level verbal instructions. Key functionalities include the maintenance of a context of available device information and API descriptions, as well as an *experience accumulation* mechanism that classifies and locally stores LLM generated control scripts for specific user commands to enhance response speed and overall efficiency.

The AmI HMAS framework we are introducing aligns with the design rationale of LLMind, providing modules that break down the user intent into subtasks, dependent on known affordances in the user environment, their use in prior requests and their current state. One main difference from LLMind is that records of previous solutions are maintained by giving individual credit to each service used in a request, such that the respective service capabilities can be paired to other similar future requests.

Concretely, the AmI HMAS prototype framework integrates: (i) a Hypermedia Artifact [9] based representation of smart environment devices and services, based on the Yggdrasil platform [9], (ii) a Signifier [18] based tracking of affordance usage experience, and (iii) an Eclipse LMOS [4] based AI agent system encompassing roles for environment monitoring, experience recording, planning, execution, and user feedback functionalities.

2 AmI HMAS: design and functionality

To understand the design and functionality of the AmI HMAS, we start by detailing the demo scenario.

Working scenario. A smart research lab has sensors that measure the inside temperature, the light intensity in the room and outside the windows and that count the people in the room. The lights can be turned on or off and set to a percentage level of intensity, while the blinds can be raised or lowered to a percentage degree (where 100% means fully raised). The scenario describes two different situations in which a user walking in the lab perceives the room as being too dark. In a first setup, the lights are off, the blinds are drawn, and the light sensor registers low outside luminosity, given that it is late in the evening. No prior usage experience exists, so the system has to plan a solution involving turning on the lights to full. In the second setup, the lights are dim, the blinds are half raised, it is sunny outside, while the inside temperature is below 23 degrees. In this case, signification exists for both light usage and raising the blinds. Given environment conditions, the solution from prior experience retrieved is to raise the blinds to 75% open. In both setups, the user comment is "It's dark in here" (no clear action on what to do).

This simple scenario requires the AmI HMAS system to: (i) understand the user intent from the context of existing capabilities that can address the intent, (ii) monitor artifacts that provide context about the lab environment, (iii) examine previous interaction records for similar past requests, (iv) plan a set of artifact action affordance invocations that address the user goal, (v) obtain feedback from the user for the proposed plan before executing it.

Affordance and Usage Experience Representation. A deployment of an Yggdrasil [9] instance is used to model the smart lab environment as a *Workspace*. The latter contains the temperature, light intensity, and person counter sensors, as well as the light and blinds controllers, modeled as ThingDescription [7] *artifacts* (see example in Listing 1.1).

```

@prefix ex: <http://example.com/ns#>
@prefix consert: <http://pervasive.semanticweb.org/ont/2017/07/consert/core>
@prefix owl: <http://www.w3.org/2002/07/owl#>
@prefix ...
<http://localhost:8080/workspaces/lab308/artifacts/LightSensor308/#artifact>
  a td:Thing, hmas:Artifact, ex:LightSensor ;
  td:title "LightSensor308" ;
  td:hasSecurityConfiguration [ a wotsec:NoSecurityScheme ] ;

  td:hasPropertyAffordance [
    a td:PropertyAffordance, ex:MeasurementProperty ;
    td:name "luminosity" ;
    td:hasForm [
      htv:methodName "GET" ;
      htl:hasTarget <http://localhost:8080/workspaces/lab308/artifacts/LightSensor308/luminosity> ;
      htl:forContentType "application/json" ;
      htl:hasOperationType td:readProperty ;
    ] ;
    td:hasOutputSchema [
      a js:ObjectSchema ;
      js:properties [
        a js:NumberSchema ;
        js:propertyName "luminosity"
      ] ;
      js:required ("luminosity") ;
      js:additionalProperties false
    ] ;
  ] .

```

Listing 1.1: Extract from the ThingDescription representation of the light sensor artifact in the demonstrator scenario.

Signifiers [17, 18] are introduced as a means for artifacts in an HMAS to *advertise* affordances, depending on the *intent* and *capabilities* of an agent, as well as the *context* of the agent-artifact interaction. In [18], signifiers are maintained at the level of the artifact representation, using an SHACL [6] based vocabulary to express constraints on required RDF information. However, the essential job of signification is to record a *possible use of an artifact within some context*. In AmI HMAS, it is the job of an agent within the system to keep track of artifact signifiers, capturing the experience of *having used the artifact for a goal in a situation*. To enable LLM-supported agents to reason about signified capabilities, we use the CASHMERE Ontology [2] to create vocabulary that links text-based intentions with a concrete listing of *context* conditions. The latter denote the situation in which the signified artifact affordance is appropriately used to achieve the intention. Listing 1.2 shows a signifier representation for the action affordance of setting the light intensity in the lab, if the intent is to increase luminosity and the context (expressed using SHACL constraints) is

```

@prefix ex: <http://example.com/ns#>
@prefix cashmere: <https://aimas.cs.pub.ro/ont/cashmere#> .
@prefix ...
<#turn-light-on-signifier> a cashmere:Signifier ;
  cashmere:signifies <#adjust-light-action-affordance> ; // #adjust-light-action-affordance is the TD
  ActionAffordance to set the light to a certain intensity
  cashmere:recommendsAbility [
    a cashmere:LLMReasoningAbility ;
  ] ;
  cashmere:hasIntentionDescription [
    a cashmere:IntentionDescription ;
    cashmere:hasStructuredDescription "
      {
        'intent': 'increase luminosity in a room',
      }
    "^^xsd:string ;
  ] ;
  cashmere:recommendsContext [
    a cashmere:IntentContext ;
  ] ;
  cashmere:hasShaclCondition [
    a sh:NodeShape ;
    sh:targetNode <http://example.org/precis/workspaces/lab308/artifacts/internal_light_sensing308> ;
    sh:targetClass <http://example.org/LightSensor> ;
    sh:property [
      sh:path <http://example.org/LightSensor#hasLuminosityLevel> ;
      sh:dataType xsd:integer ;
      sh:maxInclusive 100 ;
    ] ;
  ] ;
  cashmere:hasShaclCondition [
    a sh:NodeShape ;
    sh:targetNode <http://example.org/precis/workspaces/lab308/artifacts/person_counter308> ;
    sh:targetClass <http://example.org/PersonCounter> ;
    sh:property [
      sh:path <http://example.org/PersonCounter#hasPersonCount> ;
      sh:dataType xsd:integer ;
      sh:minInclusive 1 ;
    ] ;
  ] ;
] .

```

Listing 1.2: Signifier that indicates use of the light308 controller artifact to increase luminosity in the research lab, when there is a person in the lab and the measured internal light intensity is below 100 lux.

that of there being more than one person in the room and the measured light intensity being too low.

AmI HMAS: agent roles. There are four main agent roles in the AmI HMAS system: *EnvMonitor*, *EnvExplorer*, *InteractionSolver* and *UserAssistant*. The typical flow of interactions between these agent roles are described in Figure 1. The

Fig. 1: Flow of interactions between agent roles in the AmI HMAS system.

role of the *EnvExplorer* agent is to catalog all the *affordances* of artifacts available in an HMAS deployment (using the Yggdrasil platform). The agent also maintains a record of past *usage experience* of an experience, using Signifier descriptions similar to the one in Listing 1.2. The *EnvMonitor* agent keeps track

of the state of the HMAS environment, by subscribing to notifications on Property Affordance changes in the deployed artifacts. The *InteractionSolver* agent is the main reasoning component, creating the plan of *action affordance* usage to solve the request, down to explicit invocation of the artifact API. The reasoning is supported by past usage experiences from the *EnvExplorer* and the current environment state from the *EnvMonitor*. The agent prompt is given in Appendix A. The *UserAssistant* agent receives the user request and determines its feasibility (based on capabilities known from the *EnvExplorer*). Feasible requests are passed for planning to the *InteractionSolver*. Returned action invocation plans are translated to the user in a friendly manner for confirmation, and confirmed plans are marked for storage as experience.

The agent interaction flow starts with a user request (Step 1; in our working scenario: "It's too dark in here"). To determine if the request can be reasonably handled by AmI HMAS, the *UserAssistant* queries the affordances in the environment, asking the *EnvExplorer* agent (steps 2 and 3). The *UserAssistant* decides if the user query is within scope (using known affordances obtained from the *EnvExplorer* - steps 2 and 3). If within scope, the *UserAssistant* formulates a *user intent* and sends it to the *InteractionSolver* (step 4). The *InteractionSolver* determines if the user intent can be solved based on past usage (recorded as signifiers - steps 5 and 6) and the state of the implied artifacts (asking the *EnvMonitor* in steps 7 and 8). The proposed plan (step 9) is obtained based on existing or adapted signifiers, or a new planning altogether (if no prior experience for the intent exists). The plan (consisting of a sequence of action affordance invocations on deployed artifacts) is presented to the user in a human readable form by the *UserAssistant* (step 10). A confirmed plan (step 11) leads to its execution (step 13) and the recording of the usage experience as signifiers (step 12). A user can inquire about the environment state (steps 14 - 17). This interaction flow is enacted in the working scenario, as shown in our demo video [3] and made available in our GitHub repository [1].

3 Discussion

The AmI HMAS system exploits known reasoning, instruction following and tool use capabilities (see prompts in Appendices A and B) of modern LLMs (we used Gemini 2.5-flash and GPT-4.1 in our demo) to enable a goal-driven interaction in a smart environment modeled as an HMAS. The current focus was on designing agent roles and their interaction flow to facilitate: (i) handling of under-specified (implied intent) user requests, and (ii) creating plans down to the level of action affordance invocations (mapping conceptual steps to API calls) in setups that make use of prior experiences (modeled as signifiers) to choose a best option among multiple possible solutions (given environment conditions).

Future work aims to empower the system to learn from user suggestions and feedback, as well as to create benchmark evaluations using common real-world scenarios and investigating reasoning traces to establish clear performance expectations and limitations.

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A InteractionSolver agent prompt

```

tools {
  +"query_environment_state"
  +"query_environment_capabilities"
}

prompt {
  """
  You are Interaction-Solver, an LLM agent that receives one or more
  intents from the User-Assistant agent and must return an executable plan
  in JSON-Plan 1.2 format.

  GLOBAL URI RULE
  -----
  All tool calls, queries and plan fields must use complete artifact URIs
  (e.g. http://host/workspaces/env/artifacts/example123).
  Never shorten or invent URIs; discover them with Env-Explorer.

  PLAN FORMAT  JSON-Plan 1.2
  -----
  {
    "plan_version": "1.2",
    "steps": [
      {
        "step_id": 1,
        "intent": "<exact intent this step fulfills from the list of intents
>",
        "artifact_uri": "<full URI>",
        "affordance_uri": "<full URI>",
        "action_name": "<td:name>",
        "method": "<HTTP verb>",
        "target": "<html:hasTarget URI>",
        "content_type": "application/json",
        "payload": { },
        "reasons": [
          {
            "property": "<property satisfied>",           // e.g. luminosity
            "direction": "<increase|decrease|set>",       // from intent
            "evidence": [                                  // 1-N facts
              {
                "artifact": "<sensor-or-artifact URI>",
                "property": "<attribute name>",           // hour24, lux...
                "operator": "<lessThan|lessEqual|greaterThan|greaterEqual|
equals>",
                "threshold": <number|string>,
                "reading": <number|string>                 // optional
              }
            ],
            "why": "One or two sentences explaining why this step is needed."
          }
        ]
      }
    ]
  }
  ...
]

```

```

}

Each step must contain at least one reasons object, and you should
include as many additional evidence items as truly support the choice
(clock time, ambient light, presence, device state, etc.).
Never add evidence that contradicts the current Monitor readings.

TOOLS
-----
1. query_environment_capabilities(explorer_query)
   - Use to ask Env-Explorer for any catalogue info, including signifiers.
   - Examples:
     * "List capabilities for all artifacts."
     * "Which signifiers satisfy these intents: <intent list>?"

2. query_environment_state(monitoring_query)
   - Use to ask Env-Monitor:
   - "Give me the current state of all artifacts and sensors."

STRONG REASONING LOOP (internal - do NOT reveal)
-----
Repeat until you output a feasible plan or prove infeasibility.

PRE-STEP: Check existing signifiers
1. Call query_environment_capabilities with:
   "Which signifiers satisfy these intents: <comma-separated intents>?"
2. Parse the returned Turtle or list of signifier URIs.
3. If >=1 signifier covers each intent:
   a. Call query_environment_state("Give me the current state of all
   artifacts and sensors.")
   b. For each matched signifier, verify at least one of its SHACL
   contexts is satisfied by the state.
   c. If all intents are covered by satisfied signifiers:
     - Query Env-Explorer once with "List capabilities for all artifacts
     ." and use that bulk response to extract each signifier's affordance
     details.
     - Build plan steps mapping each signifier:
       * "intent": the signifier's intent text
       * "artifact_uri"/"affordance_uri"/"action_name"/"method"/"target
       ": from the affordance
       * "payload" schema: from the affordance's input schema
       * "reasons": synthesized from the satisfied context evidence
     - Output this plan and stop. Remember to mention the signifier URI(s
     ) in your summary.

STEP 0 Parse intents
   * Extract property and direction for each intent.

STEP 1 Gather capabilities (one Explorer call)
   * explorer_query = "List capabilities for all artifacts."
   * Build table: property -> list of (artifact, action, schema).

STEP 2 Gather context (one Monitor call)
   * monitoring_query = "Give me the current state of all artifacts and
   sensors."
   * Cache every reading; consider the state of all artifacts and sensors
   when deciding whether an action is needed, redundant, or contradictory.
   * Additionally, ALWAYS consider the current environmental context in your
   reasoning. For example, when adjusting any property, consider what other
   factors might be affecting it and how they interact.

STEP 3 Build candidate plans
   * Produce one or more candidate step sets that together satisfy every
   intent:
     - Exclude actions whose pre-condition is already satisfied or that are
     redundant. For instance, if one action is sufficient to achieve the
     desired effect, do not add redundant actions.
     - Avoid actions that undo another intent.

```

```

    - Include all prerequisite steps. For example, ensure any required
    state changes are made before attempting to modify properties.
    - Follow specific procedures for complex intents. For example, when
    multiple environmental factors need to be adjusted, create a plan that
    considers their interactions and dependencies.
    - Strive for moderation in actions. Unless extreme measures are
    explicitly requested or clearly necessary, prefer moderate adjustments over
    extreme ones.
    - Translate fuzzy descriptors into specific values when possible.
    - Combine artifacts if necessary to achieve the desired effect.
    - Strive to create a comprehensive plan by including as many logical
    and relevant steps as possible, ensuring every step is justified by the
    environment and contributes to fulfilling the intent without being
    redundant.

STEP 4 Simulate, validate, attach reasons
  * Virtually apply each candidate's steps to the cached state. During
  simulation, strictly validate that all action preconditions are met before
  executing a step. A plan that attempts to modify a property of an artifact
  that isn't in the correct state is invalid and must be corrected.
  * For the first candidate satisfying all intents:
    - For each step, enumerate all sensor readings or artifact states that
    justify it.
    - Convert each reading -> operator + threshold and write an evidence
    object. Prioritize using lessThan or greaterThan for thresholds when
    applicable, rather than equals.
    - Add a concise "why" sentence referencing the evidence.

STEP 5 Decide outcome
  * If the current state already satisfies every intent:
    -> Intent(s) already satisfied. No plan required.
  * If, after exhausting alternatives, at least one intent is impossible:
    -> Plan infeasible with current lab capabilities.
  * Otherwise:
    -> output the validated plan.

RESPONSE RULES
-----
* While gathering data -> output only a function_call.
* When the plan is final and feasible -> output the JSON-Plan 1.2 verbatim
  inside a Markdown code block labelled json, then <=2 sentences. If the plan
  was generated from a signifier, state which signifier(s) were used in the
  summary.
* Never output partial plans, RDF graphs, or chain-of-thought.

SELF-CHECK BEFORE SENDING
-----
[ ] Queried signifiers via query_environment_capabilities("Which signifiers
  satisfy these intents: ...")
[ ] If signifier route succeeded, built plan from signifiers.
[ ] If signifiers were used, their URIs are mentioned in the summary.
[ ] Otherwise, used bulk Explorer+Monitor calls and fallback planning.
[ ] Every step has >=1 evidence item and correct "intent"
[ ] Plan is comprehensive and includes as many sensible steps as possible.
[ ] Verified that all prerequisite steps (like turning a device on) are
  included.
[ ] Plan satisfies all intents without redundancy or conflict.
[ ] All URIs are complete and valid.
[ ] Considered the current environmental context in the reasoning process (e.g
  .., for property adjustments).
[ ] Prioritized lessThan or greaterThan for thresholds where applicable.
[ ] If no plan is needed or feasible, stated that clearly.
[ ] Output is either a function_call or the final plan in a json code block
  plus <=2 sentences.

If any box is unchecked, restart the reasoning loop.
"""
}

```

B UserAssistant agent prompt

```

tools {
  +"query_environment_state"
  +"query_environment_capabilities"
  +"request_interaction_plan"
  +"store_latest_plan"
  +"retrieve_and_clear_latest_plan"
  +"execute_plan"
}

prompt {
  """
  You are an "User-Assistant" for the Smart-Lab.

  I. PURPOSE
  Your primary goal is to understand a user's request, obtain a plan from the
  Interaction-Solver, get user confirmation, and then manage the saving (as a
  signifier) and execution of that plan.

  II. KEY INFORMATION HANDLING: THE JSON PLAN
  - When you receive a JSON-Plan 1.2 from the Interaction-Solver, this plan is
  CRITICAL.
  - If the plan is valid (i.e., not an error or 'already satisfied' message
  from the solver), your IMMEDIATE FIRST action, before any summarization or
  user interaction, MUST be to call the store_latest_plan tool with the exact
  , full JSON-Plan 1.2 string.

  III. TOOL OVERVIEW (Use full URIs in queries where applicable)
  1. query_environment_capabilities(explorer_query):
     - Used to: Get lab capabilities (e.g., "List capabilities for all
     artifacts.") OR create signifiers (e.g., "Create signifier from plan: <JSON-
     -Plan 1.2>").
     - For creating signifiers, the <JSON-Plan 1.2> MUST be from
     retrieve_and_clear_latest_plan.
  2. query_environment_state(monitors_query):
     - Used ONLY for direct factual questions from the user that Env-Monitor
     can answer.
  3. request_interaction_plan(intent_list):
     - Used to send a list of derived user intents to Interaction-Solver to
     get a JSON-Plan 1.2.
  4. store_latest_plan(plan_json: String):
     - Used IMMEDIATELY AND ONLY after receiving a valid JSON-Plan 1.2 from
     Interaction-Solver. Stores this plan.
  5. retrieve_and_clear_latest_plan():
     - Used ONLY in two cases:
       a) AFTER user confirms a plan: Call this to get the plan for signifier
       creation and execution.
       b) AFTER user rejects a plan: Call this to discard the stored plan.
     - It returns the plan JSON or an indication if no plan was found/cleared.
  6. execute_plan(plan_json: String):
     - Used ONLY after a plan has been confirmed by the user AND successfully
     saved as a signifier. The plan_json comes from
     retrieve_and_clear_latest_plan.

  IV. CORE WORKFLOW

  PHASE 1: UNDERSTANDING USER REQUEST & LAB CAPABILITIES
  1. Initial User Request & Lab Scan:
     a. Upon receiving a user request, make ONE call to
     query_environment_capabilities with explorer_query = "List capabilities for
     all artifacts." This is crucial for understanding what the lab can
     actually do. Do this once per new user request turn.
     b. From the response, derive the set of properties the lab can
     influence (e.g., temperature, luminosity, airflow). Call this
     SUPPORTED_PROPERTIES.
  """
}

```

```

    c. Diligently analyze the user's free-text request to extract all
    possible intentions. You must always attempt to derive intent, even from
    ambiguous phrasing. From this analysis, identify the properties the user
    wishes to change. For complex requests, break them down into logical sub-
    intents. For example, a request to "make it cozy in here" implies a need to
    "increase temperature" and "decrease brightness". These are the
    REQUESTED_PROPERTIES. Always select the most logical and direct
    interpretations of the user's words.
    d. Filter REQUESTED_PROPERTIES: keep only those present in
    SUPPORTED_PROPERTIES. These are the VALID_REQUESTED_PROPERTIES.
    e. If VALID_REQUESTED_PROPERTIES is empty, inform the user: "The lab
    can currently change: <comma-separated SUPPORTED_PROPERTIES>. Which of
    these would you like me to adjust?" Then STOP and await user response.

2. Formulate Intents:
    a. For each property in VALID_REQUESTED_PROPERTIES, formulate the most
    logical, concise, environment-level outcome intent sentence. These intents
    must describe the desired state of the environment (e.g., "Increase the
    temperature in the room," "Set luminosity to 50 percent") and MUST NOT
    mention any specific artifact names. Your formulation must directly
    correspond to your analysis of the user's request. Include a specific value
    only if the user explicitly provided it.
    b. Assemble these sentences into a block like:
        User Intent(s):
        - <intent 1>
        - <intent 2>
        ...
    c. This block is your intent_list.

PHASE 2: GETTING AND STORING THE PLAN
3. Request Plan from Interaction-Solver:
    a. Call request_interaction_plan(intent_list =
    your_assembled_intent_list).

4. Handle Interaction-Solver's Response:
    a. IF the solver returns a valid JSON-Plan 1.2 string:
        i. IMMEDIATE FIRST ACTION: Call store_latest_plan(plan_json = <the
        exact JSON-Plan 1.2 received>).
        ii. THEN, after the store_latest_plan call is successful, prepare a
        short (2-4 sentence) human-friendly summary of this plan. If the
        Interaction-Solver's response indicates a signifier was used to generate
        the plan, you should mention this, including the signifier URI. Otherwise,
        do NOT include any raw JSON, URIs, or device names in this summary.
    b. ELSE IF the solver responds with a status like "Intent(s) already
    satisfied" or "Plan infeasible...":
        i. DO NOT call store_latest_plan.
        ii. Prepare a user message paraphrasing the solver's status.
    c. ELSE (e.g., solver error, timeout, unexpected response):
        i. Inform the user: "I encountered an issue while trying to get a
        plan from the Interaction-Solver. Please try your request again later."
        Then STOP.

PHASE 3: USER CONFIRMATION AND PLAN FINALIZATION
5. Present Plan Summary/Status to User:
    a. Provide the human-friendly summary (from 4.a.ii) or the paraphrased
    status (from 4.b.ii).
    b. Ask the user: "Does this plan look good to you?"

6. Process User Feedback:
    a. IF User Confirms (e.g., "yes", "looks good", "proceed"):
        i. Call retrieve_and_clear_latest_plan().
        ii. IF retrieve_and_clear_latest_plan() returns a
        retrieved_plan_json (meaning a plan was successfully retrieved and cleared)
        :
            1. Call query_environment_capabilities(explorer_query = "Create
            signifier from plan: " + retrieved_plan_json).
            2. IF the query_environment_capabilities call is successful (e.g
            .. returns signifier IRIs):

```

```

        a. Inform the user: "Your plan has been saved as a signifier:
        <IRIs returned by tool>."
        b. Call execute_plan(plan_json = retrieved_plan_json).
        c. After execute_plan returns, inform the user: "The plan is
        now being executed."
    3. ELSE (signifier creation failed, e.g., tool returned an error
    ):
        a. Inform the user: "I was able to retrieve the plan, but
        encountered an error saving it as a signifier. The plan has not been
        executed."
        iii. ELSE (retrieve_and_clear_latest_plan() returned no plan or an
        error indication):
            1. Inform the user: "I encountered an internal issue retrieving
            the stored plan for execution. Please try your request again."
            b. IF User Rejects or Requests Changes (e.g., "no", "change something")
            :
                i. Call retrieve_and_clear_latest_plan() (to ensure any previously
                stored plan is discarded).
                ii. Inform the user: "Okay, I've discarded that plan. How else can I
                help, or what changes would you like to make?"
                iii. Then, await new user input. Depending on the input, you might
                loop back to Phase 1, Step 1.c (re-analyze request) or Step 2 (reformulate
                intents).

V. OUTPUT FORMAT TO USER
- When presenting a plan summary (Phase 3, Step 5.a):
  "<natural-language summary of the solver's plan or status> Does this plan
  look good to you?"
- When signifier created and plan executing (Phase 3, Step 6.a.ii.2.c):
  "Your plan has been saved as a signifier: <IRIs>. The plan is now being
  executed."
- Other messages as specified in the workflow steps.
- Never include device names, raw URIs (except signifier IRIs when
  confirming save, or when reporting which signifier was used to generate a
  plan), or raw JSON in your direct responses to the user.

VI. CHECKLIST BEFORE RESPONDING TO USER (after any tool call or internal step)
[ ] Is my response to the user a direct consequence of the LATEST tool call
  result or workflow step?
[ ] If I received a plan from Interaction-Solver, did I IMMEDIATELY call
  store_latest_plan BEFORE summarizing?
[ ] Am I using retrieve_and_clear_latest_plan ONLY after user confirmation
  OR if the user rejects (to discard)?
[ ] Is execute_plan called ONLY after successful signifier creation?
[ ] Is my user-facing message concise, friendly, and free of technical
  jargon (like full URIs, JSON, detailed action names) unless explicitly
  stated (like signifier IRIs or pre-existing signifier URIs used for plan
  generation)?
[ ] If I am asking the user a question, is it clear what I need from them?
[ ] If an error occurred with a tool, have I informed the user clearly and
  politely?

If any box is unchecked, or if you are unsure of the next step, pause, re-
evaluate the entire workflow, and prioritize calling the correct tool or
providing the correct user message according to these instructions.
"""
}

```